

**Palazzo
Bellisomi Vistarino
Università di Pavia**

**Department of
Molecular Medicine
Università di Pavia**

2nd YOUNG SCIENTIST WORKSHOP from basic science to clinical applications

**19-21 June 2018
at the Palazzo
Bellisomi Vistarino
Via Sant'Ennodio, 26
27100 PAVIA
ITALY**

**Further information:
www.alessandrabalduini.com**

**The workshop will be chaired by
Vittorio Abbonante
Christian Di Buduo
Alessandro Malara
Alessandra Balduini
Maria Enrica Tira
Giampaolo Minetti**

Supported by

19th – 21st June 2018, Pavia

PROGRAM

Tuesday, 19 June

10.00 – 15.30

Check-in at *Palazzo Bellisomi-Vistarino*

15.30

Transfer and Registration to the *Conference Hall “Aula Scarpa”, University of Pavia*

16.00 - 16.15

Greetings from the Organizing Committee

16.15 – 17.15

First Session

Chair: *Vittorio Abbonante, Alessandro Donada*

- *Di Buduo Christian Andrea, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy).*
Silk biomaterial and beyond: perspectives for human bone marrow engineering.
- *Francesca Basso-Valentina, Institut Gustave Roussy (Villejuif, France).*
Mechanisms of ANKRD26-related thrombocytopenia: MPL signaling deregulation.
- *Annamaria Aprile, San Raffaele Telethon Institute for Gene Therapy (Milan, Italy).*
 β -thalassemia beyond the erythropoietic defect: impaired self-renewal of hematopoietic stem cells within an altered bone marrow niche.
- *Valentin Do Sacramento, INSERM (Strasbourg, France)*
Functional properties of *in vitro* produced human platelets in a mouse model of transfusion.

17.15 – 18.15

Chair: *Christian Di Buduo, Pierre-Alexandre Laurent*

First Lectio Magistralis – Prof. Koji Eto, Center for iPS Cell Research and Application, Kyoto University.

Title: Strategy of 100B platelet manufacturing from human iPS cells.

19.00

Welcome Buffet

Wednesday, 20 June - Morning

9.30 – 10.30

Second Session

Chair: *Alessandro Malara, Federica Melazzini*

- *Vittorio Abbonante, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy).*
New insight in megakaryopoiesis and thrombopoiesis: the self-produced collagen route.
- *Loredana Bury, University of Perugia (Perugia, Italy).*
A RNA interference-based approach for the correction of autosomal dominant Glanzmann Thrombasthenia.
- *Lucia Sereni, San Raffaele Telethon Institute for Gene Therapy (Milan, Italy).*
Lentiviral-mediated gene Therapy for Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome is efficacious in restoring platelet structure and function.
- *Clara Di Vito, Humanitas Clinical and Research Center (Milan, Italy).*
NKG2A as a therapeutic target to improve NK cells alloreactivity in haploidentical hematopoietic stem cell transplanted patients.

10.30 – 11.00

Coffee Break

11.00 – 12.00

Chair: *Alessandro Malara, Vittorio Abbonante*

Second Lectio Magistralis – Prof. Mirko Pinotti, University of Ferrara.

Title: From aberrant splicing mechanisms to innovative therapeutic strategies for human genetic disorders.

12.00 – 12.45

Third Session

Chair: *Christian Di Buduo, Clara Di Vito*

- *Cinzia Civello, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy).*
Polychlorinated biphenyls reduce the kinematics contractile properties of embryonic stem cells-derived cardiomyocytes by disrupting their intracellular Ca²⁺ dynamics.
- *Giorgia Manni, University of Perugia (Perugia, Italy).*
Amniotic fluid and stem cell derived esovesicles modulate pathogenic immune responses in experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis.
- *Federica Cavalera, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy)*
In vitro maturation of mouse fully-grown germinal vesicle oocytes upon a feeder layer of selected cumulus cells enhances their meiotic and developmental competence.

12.45 – 14.00

Lunch – Buffet at the University courtyards

Group Photo

Wednesday, 20 June - Afternoon

14.00 – 15.30

Guided Tour – Visit at Museums of the University of Pavia

15.30 – 16.30

Fourth Session

Chair: *Loredana Bury, Mattia Lauriola*

- *Mathilde Reyssat, ESPCI Paris (Paris, France)*
Microfluidic model of the platelet-generating organ: beyond bone marrow biomimetics.
- *Moyra Lawrence, University of Cambridge (Cambridge, United Kingdom)*
Generating megakaryocytes at GMP grade.
- *Pierre-Alexandre Laurent, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy)*
New options for cell culture by 3D bio-printing.
- *Gabriele Pitingolo, University Paris Descartes (Paris, France)*
Mimicking complex 3D tumor microenvironment on chip.

16.30 – 16.45

Coffee Break

16.45 – 18.00

Fifth Session

Chair: *Moyra Lawrence, Nefele Giarratana*

- *Leonardo Sandrini, University of Milan (Milan, Italy).*
BDNFVal66Met polymorphism affects macrophage phenotype and worsen recovery after myocardial infarction.
- *Flavio L. Ronzoni, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy).*
Non-pressure overload animal model to monitor oxygen-sensors in cardiac hypertrophy.
- *Martina Chrisam, University of Padova (Padova, Italy).*
Dissecting the role of AMBRA1 in skeletal muscle.
- *Nefele Giarratana, KU Leuven (Leuven, Belgium).*
Impact of MICAL2 on physiological and pathological myogenic commitment.
- *Natacha Breuls, KU Leuven (Leuven, Belgium).*
Optimizing the therapeutic potential of mesodermal progenitors for the treatment of muscular dystrophies.

20.30

Italian pizza!!

Thursday, 21 June

9.30 – 10.45

Sixth Session

Chair: *Eti Femia, Francesca Basso-Valentina*

- *Antonella De Luca, University of Perugia (Perugia, Italy).*
Tryptophan derivatives prevent the development of anti-FVIII antibodies in an experimental model of hemophilia A by the engagement of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor.
- *Carlo Zaninetti, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy).*
Biallelic mutations in PTPRJ cause a novel form of inherited thrombocytopenia.
- *Alessandro Donada, INSERM-Université Paris Diderot (Paris, France).*
Loss of Filamin A induces a defective megakaryocytic maturation through RhoA pathway activation.

- *Raghavendra Palankar, University of Greifswald (Greifswald, Germany).*
Nano/Micropatterned biomimetic surfaces and live bacteria on microarrays for assessing platelet function and dynamics.
- *Francesca Calcaterra, Humanitas Clinical and Research Center (Milan, Italy).*
Endothelial dysfunction in patients with unprovoked venous thromboembolism is mediated by constitutive upregulation of TNFSF15 and its receptor TNFRSF25.

10.45 – 11.00

Coffee Break

11.00 – 12.00

Group discussion:

How to write a successful collaborative Grant - Chaired by Prof. Alessandra Balduini

12.00 – 12.45

Seventh Session

Chair: *Martina Chrisam, Palankar Raghavendra*

- *Aurora De Acutis, University of Pisa (Pisa, Italy).*
Novel fabrication approaches for multiscale and multimaterial scaffolds
- *Mattia Lauriola, University of Bologna (Bologna, Italy).*
Modulation of ERBB signaling from tissue homeostasis to cancer progression.
- *Alessandro Malara, University of Pavia (Pavia, Italy).*
Cellular fibronectin isoforms in physiology and pathology.

12.45 – 13.00

Closing remarks.

See you at the 3rd Young Scientist Workshop!

NOTES

- The official language will be English.
- There will be series of 15 minute talks (10 minutes for the presentation and 5 for the discussion).

ACCOMMODATION

We will cover the costs for the overnight stay at:

[Palazzo Bellisomi Vistarino](#),

Via Sant'Ennodio n. 26

27100, PAVIA

LOCATION

The conference will be host in the historical “Aula Scarpa”, in the Central Palace of the University of Pavia, C.so Strada Nuova n. 65, 27100, PAVIA

RECEIPT OF PAYMENT AND CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

The receipt of payment will be provided, together with the certificate of attendance, at the end of the Workshop, on Thursday 21st.

LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

- Prof.ssa Alessandra Balduini (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Prof. Koji Eto (Center for iPS Cell Research and Application, University of Kyoto, Kyoto, Japan)
- Prof. Giampaolo Minetti (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Prof. Mirko Pinotti (University of Ferrara, Ferrara, Italy)
- Prof.ssa Maria Enrica Tira (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Abbonante Vittorio (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Aprile Annamaria (San Raffaele Telethon Institute for Gene Therapy, Milan, Italy)
- Bassani Giulia Alessandra (Silk Biomaterials s.r.l., Como, Italy)
- Basso-Valentina Francesca (Institut Gustave Roussy, Villejuif, France)
- Biagiotti Marco (Silk Biomaterials s.r.l., Como, Italy)
- Breuls Natacha (KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium)
- Bury Loredana (University of Perugia, Perugia, Italy)
- Calcaterra Francesca (Humanitas Clinical and Research Center, Milan, Italy)
- Cavalera Federica (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Chrisam Martina (University of Padova, Padova, Italy)
- Civello Cinzia (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- De Acutis Aurora (University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy)
- De Luca Antonella (University of Perugia, Perugia, Italy)
- Di Buduo Christian Andrea (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Di Vito Clara (Humanitas Clinical and Research Center, Milan, Italy)
- Do Sacramento Valentin (INSERM, Strasbourg, France)
- Donada Alessandro (INSERM-Université Paris Diderot, Paris, France)
- Femia Eti Alessandra (Fondazione IRCCS Ca' Granda, Milan, Italy)
- Giarratana Nefele (KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium)
- Laurent Pierre-Alexandre (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Lauriola Mattia (University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy)
- Lawrence Moyra (University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom)
- Malara Alessandro (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Manni Giorgia (University of Perugia, Perugia, Italy)
- Melazzini Federica (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Palankar Raghavendra (University of Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany)
- Pitingolo Gabriele (Univeristy Paris Descartes, Paris, France)
- Reyssat Mathilde (ESPCI Paris, Paris, France)
- Ronzoni Flavio (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Sandrini Leonardo (University of Milan, Milan, Italy)
- Sereni Lucia (San Raffaele Telethon Institute for Gene Therapy, Milan, Italy)
- Soprano Paolo Maria (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)
- Trapasso Riccardo (ISENET, Milan, Italy)
- Vincoli Valentina Teodolinda (Silk Biomaterials s.r.l., Como, Italy)
- Zaninetti Carlo (University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy)

